

Critical mathematics education and social movements: Possibilities in an LGBT+ host house

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The LGBT+ community has historically been excluded from different spaces and has suffered with the prejudice and violence in Brazil and worldwide. The school has a fundamental role in the struggle for a less prejudiced society that respects and values differences. Through a study carried out in an LGBT+ host house, we will discuss in this article how spaces like this can become spaces for transformation and that bringing knowledge produced in these places to school and, specifically for mathematics classes, is a way to contribute to the struggle for a more just society.

Introduction

In the book *Pedagogia da Indignação*, more specifically in the chapter “Alfabetização e Miséria”, Paulo Freire (2016) talks about an experience in Recife/PE, where he was walking with an educator friend in a slum in the city where many families lived from what they collected from a local garbage dump. The main question discussed was: “What to do in a context where many people are denied their humanity?” This is a recurring reflection of/in this book in which the author places/identifies indignation as essential for mobilizations to happen and changes to take effect.

In another chapter of the same book, entitled “Do assassinato de Galdino Jesus dos Santos – índio Pataxó”, Freire reflects on what happened in the early hours of April 20, 1997, when a chief was murdered in Brasília. The indigenous leader, who was resting at a bus stop, was found by five young men who arrived by car and set him on fire. When they were accused of this inhumane act, they justified it by saying they believed he was a person on the street. Freire presents his indignation about this dehumanizing fact:

What a strange thing, playing killing Indian, killing people. I keep thinking here, plunged into the abyss of a profound perplexity, amazed at the intolerable perversity of these young men disfiguring themselves, in the environment in which they have decreased instead of growing (Freire, 2016, p. 75).

This type of violence, suffered mainly by groups that we call underrepresented, is unfortunately common in our country. In this work, we will highlight the LGBT+ community (Lesbians, Gays, Bisexuals, Transsexuals, Transvestites, Transgenders and more) that has faced several struggles in our country. The reports of the Gay Group of Bahia carried out annually registered 329 deaths of LGBT+ people due to hate crimes in the year 2019 (Grupo

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Gay Bahia, 2019). In other words, several LGBT+ people are murdered in Brazil on account of their gender identity or sexual orientation.

These statistical data and the situations presented by Freire are examples of oppressions that underrepresented groups have faced in Brazil. When we look at the participation of these groups in decision-making spaces, such as political spaces, it has been very low, which can lead to the difficulty of public policies being designed and implemented in order to alleviate these situations of violence.

In Brazil, the National Congress is the national institution that exercises legislative power in Brazil and is divided into a chamber of deputies and a federal senate, where the chamber of deputies is understood as representatives of the people and has representatives in proportion to the number of voters in a given state and the senate has 3 representatives from each Brazilian state.

According to research by the National Congress, in the four-year term that began in 2019, of the 513 representatives of the people at the national congress, only 77 were female, 125 black and only one admitted to belonging to the LGBT+ community. These data do not portray the reality of the Brazilian population, because, for example, the Superior Electoral Court (TSE) points out that women constitute 51.3% of the total voters. As this data shows, we can think about representativity in the political space. However, when we discuss participation in formal or informal spaces, including the media, universities and the work market, we are also talking about representativity

As a result, underrepresented groups have been participating in social and collective movements in the search for a more just society. Butler (2018) highlights the importance of the struggle of social movements and emphasizes that not all social movements are necessarily democratic, therefore, they need to be looked at carefully.

Keeping this argument in mind, we emphasize the importance of the role of social movements in the struggle for a more just society, promoting attitudes that favour the conquest of spaces by underrepresented groups to assist in the search to overcome stigmas and break barriers. The work developed in these spaces can also be understood as a promoter of learning, so the struggle is pedagogical (Gutstein, 2018). As an example, we can mention the work developed by some LGBT+ host houses in Brazil that are spaces that offer support to people who have been expelled from their homes on account of their sexual orientation or gender identity. The doctoral research (Barros, in progress), with which this article is linked, was conducted in one of these spaces. Information about the research will be presented below.

Conducting the research

The research reported in this article was carried out in a host house for LGBT+ people called Casassa in the city of Presidente Prudente/SP. The production of data took place in the months of August and September 2019 and the researcher sought to get involved in all the activities promoted, in addition to offering conversation circles.

Casassa is not for profit and everyone who works there is a volunteer. Its creation took place at the II Diversity Week that took place in the city of Presidente Prudente/SP in 2017. At this event there were several moments of reflection on gender and sexuality and in one of the activities the discussion arose about the need to have a permanent space so that welcoming work could be done to provide for LGBT+ people who were expelled from home and furthermore, that it was a space to hold discussions on relevant topics.

Casassa, not having any type of financing, carries out its work using money from donations and events that are promoted by volunteers. Every month there is a bazaar, called Bazarsasso, at which items donated to the house are sold and all the money goes to the local expenses. Educational and cultural events such as parties, English courses and workshops have already been held and promoted by the Casassa team.

Volunteers' work is organized by working groups. This work involves: reception, dissemination, donations, education, financial, legal and events. Casassa has two main purposes: welcoming LGBT+ people and carrying out cultural and educational activities. Thus, the word "welcoming" has two possible understandings, being a space for temporary housing of people who were expelled from home on account of their sexuality or gender identity and also a meeting place for discussions and interactions focused on the LGBT+ movement.

In August 2019, the researcher had his first face-to-face contact with the house, participating in meetings of the volunteer team, of which seven were interviewed throughout the month. The purpose of the interviews was to understand how Casassa originated, how work has been developed, relations with the community, the question of educational activities and the place of mathematics in this space. Participants were informed about the purpose and nature of the interviews and signed the Free and Informed Consent Form. The interviews were recorded in audio.

In September, two circles of thematic conversations were held. The first promoted discussions on representativity, focusing on the presence of LGBT+ people in politics. The second conversation circle dealt with the issue of visibility and stereotype thinking about how LGBT+ people are portrayed in diverse media. Casassa volunteers participated in the conversation circles, welcomed and also generated interested people from the community. In this stage, audio recordings were made during the activities and shortly after finishing the activity, the researcher made notes on important facts that happened.

The format of the conversation circles was based on Paulo Freire's (1987) cultural circles. These collective moments of dialogue sought to respect the knowledge of each participant and promote a democratic environment to reflect on reality inherent to the LGBT+ community. Critical Mathematical Education was used to help us think about the themes of representativity, visibility and stereotype thinking in the conversation circles. Looking at the mathematics that is involved in these processes helped us to compose the electoral system in the political space and to reflect on possibilities for social change. The theory from Critical Mathematics Education used to support the design of activities is the reading and writing of the world with Mathematics (Gutstein, 2006), where mathematics is used to promote

discussions that help in the understanding of situations in society and also helps in the realization of transformations.

Gutstein (2006) makes use of investigative activities that make a movement that starts from issues for the community and goes to the classroom. We sought to be inspired by this movement to bring issues that were relevant to the LGBT+ community to be topics of conversation circles. In addition, the construction of proposals and choice of mathematical tools and strategies had as protagonists the participants who reflect and put mathematics into action.

At this point in the research, the transcripts were having been completed, both of the interviews and of the conversation circles. The records have been organized and relationships are being established with the researcher's notes. This is a complex process that is not linear. The analysis has been carried out taking into account the research question, the objectives and the aspects that stood out in the data.

A close look has been started in order to understand what possibilities of reading and writing the world with mathematics can emerge from a social movement. Based on these reflections, I bring below some notes that help us to reflect on how Casassa (as a social movement) collaborates with the community in which it is inserted.

A host house changing a community

Casassa's proposal is to be a welcoming home, but this goes beyond the idea of housing. José brings this perspective by talking about how his friend Larissa, who is a transvestite, has experienced society as not safe for LGBT+ people:

This whole neighbourhood is a place and having a transvestite living two blocks from here, there is Cláudio who will live two blocks from here too, because having Casassa makes these people more comfortable in that space. I remember when Larissa, this transvestite friend from the neighbourhood lived in another place, a neighbourhood far away and I went to visit her one day in the morning, we went from her house to the bakery which is two blocks away and just walking this way I came back tired, because there were a lot of whispered looks and comments with us passing by. They were simply looking, they didn't need to speak or shout anything, but I realized that Larissa was attentive all the time. That is why I hope that the whole community can be here at Casassa and that they get to know the LGBT + people to make the whole neighbourhood more welcoming, changing the structure of the place.

One of Casassa's goals is to create a host and support network that goes beyond the physical location restricted to the host home. In this quest, making a simple exercise like going to the bakery safer for LGBT+ people are a necessary exercise. However, for this to happen structural changes are necessary for society to understand the importance of respecting differences.

Another Casassa volunteer, Davi, sees the host house as a motivator for discussions on the reality of the LGBT+ community, after all it leads people to think about this, even though sometimes the discussions are initially marked by stereotypes:

I think it influences in a positive and negative way. We have seen both things happen. Because it is an LGBT+ host house, it has the common sense that it is a place that is related to sex, so there are a lot of people who look here with a crooked eye and do not have the courage to come and ask what is happening and are judging. The positive impact is that people in need of care have a hope of knowing that there is a space like this.

This discomfort highlighted by Davi helps to get people out of their comfort zone and makes them think. In this reflection on the discussions on the reality of the LGBT+ community, it is possible that there will be an appreciation of Casassa and consequently of the LGBT+ community. Corroborating José's observations, Davi also reinforces the importance of the existence of host houses so that LGBT+ people can feel more secure in the process of developing their sexuality or gender identity.

Another interviewee, Olga, reports that the volunteers are beginning to understand the impacts of Casassa on society and that the host house represents hope for those who are expelled from home, in addition to being a space that promotes necessary discussions on LGBT+ reality:

It has a significant impact in many ways. First the impact of the service provided, let's say that having this welcome is a refuge for these people, not only for those who are expelled, but those who were there without having a reference and did not understand their sexual orientation and gender identity and, suddenly, to see people thinking "Ah, I'm like them". It is an impact of visibility, because it started to be talked about this subject in a more open way. We do not know very well if it reached certain layers of society and if we arrived in many places, but we had contact with some businesses that offered support to us. Universities too and social movements themselves. I think the main thing was visibility as a whole. I see in my own family, when I say that I am working on this project, people start asking me, "What is Casassa?", "Do you accept it?", "Do you have families that expel children from home for this?". Have! So, it was this opening to a reality that sometimes these people did not know. We need to understand that there are realities different from ours and that something needs to be done.

A common response in the interviews was that the interviewees did not want a host house for LGBT+ people to be needed, after all, nobody should be expelled from their home on account of their sexuality or gender. However, we must emphasize that it is important to have host houses such as Casassa in the current society.

About the presence of mathematics in the daily life of Casassa, the volunteers had a little difficulty in saying about aspects that could be seen in their activities. It was evidenced by the interviewees in the financial issues of managing the house and the bazaar that is held to raise money. However, at no time was mathematics seen as a promoter of social and political discussions. The conversation circles sought to change this perspective.

When conducting the conversation circles, it was possible to put mathematics into practice, with mathematics providing a reading and writing of the world. In this sense, themes related to representativity, visibility and stereotypes were discussed. These are pertinent issues that reflect on how society views the LGBT+ community and the participation of this group in in a range of spaces. During the first conversation circle, for

example, we reflected on how underrepresented groups participate in the Chamber of Deputies, which is one of the houses of the Brazilian legislative power.

We used concepts such as percentage to compare the presence of underrepresented groups in these political spaces and in the community, and we find that there is a large discrepancy. We reflected on the reasons for this to happen from a critical perspective. These groups have historically been excluded from electoral processes, as many political parties have been concerned with issues that address the exclusive demands of a majority of the population.

In addition, we reflected on the electoral process, after all, the elections in Brazil are made by proportional votes by party. So, the votes destined for a certain candidate do not necessarily go to them, but these votes can help to elect another person from the same party. This proportional process could be a problem in the search for representativity.

Research participants showed themselves to be engaged during the discussions. The reality data on the representation of minorities surprised the participants in the conversation circle. Furthermore, mathematics helped to look to the future and think in an ideal context.

The need for greater participation by underrepresented groups in political and other spaces was evidenced so that, through public policies, transformations can be made showing a more inclusive society with more respect. Providing this type of debate in a space like Casassa proved to be necessary so that through struggle we can increasingly learn about human diversity. These were the conclusions of the participants in the conversation circles, who came to see mathematics as a possibility to discuss social and political issues.

At this point, we can see the importance of using mathematics from a critical perspective so that people who participated in that activity could reflect on the reality of the LGBT+ community and the participation of this group in politics.

These important discussions promoted in a space like Casassa can and should be taken to schools. However, this is not a simple task, since the advancement of conservatism has made it difficult for discussions about gender and sexuality to be held in Brazilian schools. However, teachers must take on this important task of promoting these discussions in their classrooms.

Conclusions

For change to happen, we cannot be unaware of the world's problems. We must be indignant about injustices, as proposed by Freire (2016) and in order to collaborate with the struggle of the oppressed, we must promote a pedagogy of resistance, where one learns to fight, fighting. Involvement with social movements in this sense is shown to be powerful, after all it is in these spaces that underrepresented groups organize themselves and carry out mobilizations seeking a more just society.

Through the realization of this research, we see that a space like Casassa is a pedagogical space. The engagement in the struggle of the LGBT+ movement can take place in several ways, but it is essential for us to overcome the prejudices that this community has suffered.

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We as teachers are invited to be in these spaces participating in these discussions, but it is also important that we take these debates to our classes.

Mathematics showed its potential to collaborate with the reading and writing of the world when used from a critical perspective. The activities used in the circles helped us to think about ways to transform the reality of the LGBT+ community, which has still been largely excluded from society.

We fight for a less prejudiced society in which we will no longer have, for example, people being expelled from their homes on account on their sexuality or gender identity. In this sense, we believe that mathematics has the potential to support much needed discussions about diversity and difference.

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